

substance (as trimethyl silyl ether derivatives) showed it to be a mixture of campesterol (1.07%, M^+ 472), stigmasterol (4.82%, M^+ 484), β -sitosterol (92.5%, M^+ 486), and an unidentified substance, the two-ion peaks 343, 386 are different from those of β -sitosterol.

Benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 1) and ethyl acetate fractions were subjected to preparative layer chromatography on silica-gel using benzene-pyridine-formic acid (36 : 9 : 5) to yield BVI, BVII and BVIII, and two minor bands in order of increasing R_f values.

A mixture of BVI (100 mg), dimethyl sulphate, anhydrous potassium carbonate and dry acetone were refluxed together for 8 h. After the usual work up and purification over silica gel column it was crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH, m.p. 162-164°, (M^+ 622). It was characterised as I-4', II-4', I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7', hexa-*O*-methyl[I-6, II-8]biflavone (agathisflavone) by nmr studies and comparison with those of the authentic sample⁴. The two minor bands were methylated to give the same methyl ether and were detected as mono- and di-*O*-methyl agathisflavone. The two fractions BVII and BVIII were characterised as quercetin and kaemferol, respectively by m.p., m.m.p. and co-tlc.

The acetone extract gave two bands which were characterised as betulinic acid and quercetin-3-glucoside (m.p. 221-24°). The identity was finally confirmed by direct comparison with authentic samples⁵.

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Platinum-Graphite Polarizable Electrode System for Non-aqueous Biamperometric Indication. Estimation of Mercaptans with Iodine

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RECENT adoption of the platinum-graphite combination for biamperometric indication involving aqueous and partially non-aqueous determinations¹⁻⁴ prompted to explore the condi-

tions suitable for its applicability in systems exclusively non-aqueous. The present communication reports an attempt to estimate small amounts of various mercaptans with iodine in a solution of *N,N*-dimethylformamide.

Experimental

The experimental procedure with its circuit arrangement was essentially the same as employed earlier for aqueous determinations¹. A wax-impregnated graphite and a micro-platinum electrode suitably fixed in a rubber disc at a fixed interspace ~3 cm, constituted the electrode assembly between which was impressed a constant emf obtained from a battery-operated potentiometer, with graphite as positive.

All chemicals used were of the analytical grade except when stated otherwise. *N,N*-Dimethylformamide (E. Merck) prior to use was kept in contact with sodium carbonate for 48 h with occasional shaking and the decanted liquid was distilled for the fraction boiling between 148.5-149.5°. Test solutions of the given mercaptan (Fluka samples of *n*-butyl- and benzylmercaptans, 2-mercaptoethanol and thiophenol) as also of the titrant, iodine (B.D.H.) were prepared in the above solvent; these were standardised⁵ using copper(II) chloride for the mercaptans and sodium thiosulphate in aqueous medium for iodine.

A known amount of the mercaptan solution was taken in the titration vessel and the volume was adjusted to 30 ml, before addition of iodine from a semi-microburette. The cell current was measured (at a constant polarising emf varied in the range 100-350 mV) with a sensitive galvanometer after a lapse of usually 1 min following each addition. The solution was kept stirred throughout using a magnetic stirrer. Equivalence points were obtained from the corresponding current-volume plots. A set of representative results for the above substances is returned in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

As the present estimation is based on the oxidation of the mercaptan (according to the general scheme followed by Yoshimura and Miyamoto⁶, *i.e.* $2\text{DMF.R-SH} + \text{KI}_3 \rightarrow 2\text{DMF.R-S} + \text{KI} + 2\text{HI}$), presence of any unused iodine generates the current indicating couple I_3^-/I^- . This prevailing on completion of the process, introduces an abrupt onset of the cell current. The titration curves therefore, as anticipated, are found to be of the reversed L-shape with well defined breaks.

It is noted further that the polarising emf, requisite for obtaining reliable current magnitudes, is slightly greater than that required for similar work in an aqueous medium. However, it affects in no way either the general nature of the corresponding titration curves or the location of the end points; it enlarges simply the cell current.

NOTES

TABLE 1—NON-AQUEOUS DETERMINATION OF MERCAPTANS USING PLATINUM-GRAPHITE BIAMPEROMETRIC INDICATION

Mercaptan	Approximate molarity	Amount of mercaptan (mg)		Error %
		Taken	Found	
n-Butyl mercaptan	9.07×10^{-4}	2.456	2.472	+0.65
	1.36×10^{-3}	3.684	3.663	-0.57
	2.26×10^{-3}	6.140	6.113	-0.43
	4.08×10^{-3}	11.052	11.102	+0.45
	5.44×10^{-3}	14.736	13.665	-0.48
Benzyl mercaptan	6.27×10^{-4}	2.340	2.361	+0.89
	9.41×10^{-4}	3.510	3.534	+0.68
	2.19×10^{-3}	8.190	8.163	-0.32
	3.14×10^{-3}	11.700	11.637	-0.53
	4.39×10^{-3}	16.380	16.454	+0.45
2-Mercaptoethanol	8.31×10^{-4}	1.948	1.967	+0.97
	1.24×10^{-3}	2.922	2.899	-0.78
	2.90×10^{-3}	6.818	6.778	-0.58
	4.57×10^{-3}	10.714	10.753	+0.36
	6.64×10^{-3}	15.584	15.663	+0.50
Thiophenol	6.77×10^{-4}	2.240	2.264	+1.07
	1.69×10^{-3}	5.600	5.632	+0.56
	2.71×10^{-3}	8.960	9.028	+0.75
	4.06×10^{-3}	13.440	13.366	-0.55
	5.08×10^{-3}	16.800	16.735	-0.38

The curves, in general, are similar to those obtainable with the conventional identical platinum or other electrode pairs^{7,8}. The dissimilarity of the electrodes in the present case offers an additional advantage in yielding sharp breaks facilitating easy and unambiguous determination. The accuracy and the reproducibility of results even in low concentration range (Table 1) illustrate that the present platinum-graphite electrode system is conveniently applicable for biamperometric indication in non-aqueous medium as well.

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